

LISTENING IS AN ESSENTIAL SIGN OF EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: This article is about listening comprehension, which is one of the types of speech competence, and it is highlighted that attentive listening is important in communicative, interactive, perceptive types of communication.

Key words: addressee, communication act, communication aspect, mental activity, linguistic combinations, acceptable input.

СЛУШАНИЕ – НЕОБХОДИМЫЙ ПРИЗНАК ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

Аннотация: В данной статье речь идет об аудировании, которое является одним из видов речевой компетенции, и подчеркивается, что внимательное слушание важно в коммуникативных, интерактивных, перцептивных видах общения.

Ключевые слова: адресат, коммуникативный акт, коммуникативный аспект, мыслительная деятельность, языковые сочетания, допустимый ввод.

INTRODUCTION

Since speech activity results from the active action of both parties, it is wrong to say that all responsibility for perfect communication rests with the addressee, that is, the speaker. Knowing how to listen is also one of the most difficult aspects of communication acts. Unless both parties do their best, interpersonal communication between them remains a futile endeavor. Especially in general education schools, as a result of inattentive listening of students who are not capable of science, it leads to the fact that this subject is not mastered properly, assignments are not completed on time, and as a result, they become passive students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Let's take the opinion of Alisher Navoi's admirer and friend Husayn Vaiz Koshifi about the conditions of becoming a disciple: "If they ask what the building of discipleship is built on, answer that it is built on will." If they ask you about something, say that it is heaven and obedience. If they ask you what is samo' (hearing) and obedience, then tell them that what the teacher says is to hear it with the ears of the soul, to accept it with the whole heart, and to do it in practice through the organs of the body. If they ask what is good for a disciple, say that it is pure faith, because only faith brings a person to his will." [1.198]

In this regard, Kaikovus writes: "O child, if you can, don't run away from hearing words, a person develops eloquence by hearing words. First of all, it can be proven like this, if a boy is born to a mother, if they make a place under the ground and give him milk and take care of him in that place, if his mother and midwife do not speak to him, if the boy does not hear anyone's words, then when he grows up, he will be dumb. Those who do not see, all the dumb will be deaf." [2.41]

But listening is also different. Some people sit silently listening to any speech, any song, the melodies and meanings of the words do not reach their heart. "If a cow bleats while you are talking, it will not affect you, but the person looking after the cow..." (Abdullah Qahhor). Someone else will quickly understand what the flute or drum is saying. Because such people pay attention to the thoughts of their interlocutors and listen to their words with their body and soul. That is why

our forefathers used to listen politely to their interlocutors, especially older people. Even when they listened, they listened with special attention, not with enthusiasm or absent-mindedness. Especially those who listened silently to insults and reprimands given by adults. [3.7]

RESULTS

So, the emergence of speech begins with hearing. Students should pay more attention to the meaning of the word during the listening comprehension process. It can be said that the concept of listening is usually associated with the word attention. Listen carefully! when spoken, the emphasis on listening comprehension is often increased.

Attention is the orientation of mental activity and concentration on an object of certain importance for a person (stable or situational concentration). Orientation refers to the selective nature of mental activity, voluntary or involuntary selection of an object. When a student listens to what the teacher is saying at school, he has consciously chosen this activity of listening, his attention is subjugated to this purpose. The direction of the student's mental activity is expressed when the student concentrates on the content of the educational material without being distracted by something else. [4.69]

Krashen's ideas on listening comprehension skills are described in A. Murodova's article entitled "The role of listening comprehension skills in mother tongue education":

DISCUSSION

Attention to listening comprehension skills reached a new level in language learning theory in connection with Krashen's idea of "comprehensible input". According to him, the provision of material appropriate to the learner's level in language learning ensures the effectiveness of this process. In psycholinguistics, it is said that in the process of hearing and understanding, the human mind works in a top-down and bottom-up direction. In the bottom-up approach, the listener understands the flow of speech from phonemes to sentences or text. It is called "bottom-up" because the reception process proceeds from small units to large units (phoneme, syllable, word, phrase, syntagma, sentence...).

In the top-down approach, the listener first makes a conclusion about the general content of the text, and then, based on this conclusion, understands the sentences, phrases and words in the text. This approach is called "top-down" because the understanding proceeds from the big unit to the small ones (the general content of the text and the sentence, the contextual meaning of the word). A "bottom-up" or "top-down" approach to understanding, or both, can be used.

I. In Azimova's scientific work on the topic "Psycholinguistic study of the content perception of newspaper texts in Uzbek", listening comprehension was studied experimentally. After listening to the text, the participants of the experiment first record the linguistic combinations they remember, and then write a statement based on the text. I. Azimova describes the linguistic combinations remembered during the initial listening process and the process of understanding the narrative text written by the participants of the experiment by comparing it with the original text. According to him, the process of understanding occurs through cognitive actions such as decoding of words and phrases, their place in the sentence, clarification of connections, determining the place of the word in the connection of meaningful blocks, understanding the place of sentences in the meaningful block, their interconnection, clarifying the connection of meaningful blocks to the general content of the text. Text perception is a multi-channel and multi-level process, and if several channels work at its lower levels, these channels are combined at higher levels, because at lower levels the components of the text appear as a perceptual unit. At higher levels, these units combine to make it possible to perceive the content of the text as a whole.[5.13]

CONCLUSIONS

For this reason, narrations and dictations, as a reliable tested method in mother tongue education, have a great role and importance in listening comprehension. One of the main tasks of mother tongue education is the consistent development of high school students' ability to listen and understand information correctly. Mastering these is important not only in the emergence of communication, but also in the early stages of diligently mastering each area. The fact that dictation exams are held even for entrants to study in the field of aviation is a proof of our opinion. The reason is that when aircraft takeoff or landing information is relayed to the controller by walkie-talkie, a slight lapse in listening or understanding can lead to a major disaster. That's why listening comprehension is one of the urgent issues in the competence of speech communication that should be perfectly taught.

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